

DELAMINATION FRACTURE AND CORE CRUSHING IN COMPOSITE SANDWICH BEAMS

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SUMMARY

The paper deals with the nonlinear response of composite sandwich beams subject to static and dynamic out-of-plane loading. The internal structure of such composite systems gives rise to complex damage and failure mechanisms, which include multiple delamination of the skin, interfacial fracture at the skin-core interface and core crushing. The objective of the study is to analyse how different damage mechanisms interact and how these interactions affect the mechanical behavior of the system. The study refers to the model system of a sandwich beam, continuously supported by a rigid plane and subject to out-of-plane loading; the problem is studied using the schematic of a multiply delaminated beam on a nonlinear Winkler foundation. Static and dynamic analyses are performed and the influence on damage propagation of the initial position and size of delaminations in the skin and the constitutive parameters of skin and core are analysed.

The skin-core interaction strongly affects the fracture parameters of the delaminations. When the foundation is elastic, a shielding phenomenon is observed on increasing the ratio between the stiffness of the core and the flexural stiffness of the skin. The same ratio controls phenomena of localized amplification, which occur when the delamination tips come close to each other, as well as phenomena of localized shielding. These local effects can induce accelerated growth of the delaminations or crack arrests due to the presence of energy barriers. Under dynamic loading conditions, inertial effects enrich the response with new regimes of behavior leading for instance to oscillations in the arms of the delaminated beam which are characterized by different frequencies and amplitudes that favour damage propagation.

Keywords: sandwich beams, composites, delamination fracture, dynamic response, impact

INTRODUCTION

The combination of high strength, high stiffness and light weight make composite sandwiches attracting material systems for naval, aerospace, transportation and other advanced structural applications. Many of these applications are characterized by the presence of severe dynamic loads (for example explosions, gust and sonic boom pulses or high velocity impact) that require high damage tolerance and resistance and energy absorption capabilities. Understanding the behaviour of sandwich systems under such type of loads and defining the conditions that minimize their negative effects while optimizing strength, energy dissipation and other mechanical properties is an important target.

Currently produced composite sandwich systems are usually made of high stiffness and high strength laminated face sheets that are joined to light weight cores made of plastic foam or low strength honeycomb structures. The combination of high-strength face sheets and light-weight cores leads to superior performance with respect to monolithic beams of the same mass. Experimental results [1-4] have shown that the internal structure of sandwich systems can give rise to complex damage and failure mechanisms, like compressive and shear failures of the core, local indentation with core crushing, skin wrinkling and skin and core-skin delamination. While several studies have been conducted to separately analyse the different failure modes and define failure maps in order to optimize the sandwich design [e.g. 5,6], the problem of the interaction of the different damage mechanisms and its effects on damage propagation and mechanical performance under dynamic loading conditions is not yet fully understood.

Multiple delamination is a dominant failure mechanism of laminated sheets when they are subject to dynamic out-of-plane loadings. It was shown in [7-8] that static and dynamic interaction between delamination cracks controls their propagation and have important effects on the overall mechanical response and damage resistance. Different combinations of shielding and amplification phenomena (i.e., increase/decrease of fracture parameters with respect to the values for the cracks alone in the system) deeply affect the propagation of damage and give rise to phenomena such as local snap-back and snap-through instabilities in the macrostructural response, crack-pull along and crack arrest. Energy dissipation due to the creation of new fracture surfaces depend on how the cracks propagate, with simultaneously propagating cracks generally leading to higher dissipation.

In sandwich beams, delaminations may arise between the laminae of the skin and also at the core-skin interface. Moreover, their static and dynamic interaction is expected to be deeply affected by the presence of the core whose non-linear elastic-plastic behaviour plays a fundamental role in controlling how the energy from a dynamic load is distributed and dissipated in the structure.

The objective of this study is to analyse how the skin-core interaction affects the interaction and propagation of multiple delaminations in the skin. The analyses refer to the model system of a sandwich beam, continuously supported by a rigid plane and subject to out-of-plane loading. In this configuration overall bending effects are not present and the analysis can focus on the fundamental aspects of the local damage phenomena. The upper face sheet, which is subjected to the external load, is decomposed into sub-beams, which represent intact portions of the face sheet. The core is modelled as a non-linear Winkler foundation. Static and dynamic analyses are performed and the effects of the initial position and size of the delaminations and of the constitutive parameters of skin and core on damage propagation are analysed.

THEORETICAL MODELS

A multiply delaminated sandwich beam with composite face sheets, a homogeneous core and subject to out-of-plane loading is studied. The beam is assumed to be continuously supported by a rigid plane so that overall bending is absent. The upper face of the sandwich is modelled as a beam resting on a nonlinear elastic-plastic Winkler foundation that describes the response of the core (Fig.1).

Fig.1 Sandwich beam and sub-beam subdivision in (a) static and (b) dynamic models.

The delaminated beam is subdivided into sub-beams following two different schemes for static and dynamic problems. In the static model the subdivision is defined by vertical sections at the crack tip positions and longitudinal sections along the delaminations (Fig.1a). In the dynamic model the subdivision in sub-beams is realized only with longitudinal sections at the delamination planes that cover the whole length of the beam (Fig.1b). In both models sub-beams are described by first order shear deformation beam theory. The generic sub-beam k (in the following, sub-beams are numbered from top to bottom and from left to right) has height h_k and its cross sectional moment of inertia and area per unit width are $I_k = h_k^3 / 12$ and $S_k = h_k$. The generalized displacements of its centroidal axis are the axial and transverse displacements u_k and w_k and the rotation φ_k . The stress resultants per unit width are the axial force N_k , shear force V_k and bending moment M_k . The compatibility equations are:

$$\varphi_k = -w_k' + \gamma_k, \quad \varepsilon_k = u_k', \quad \chi_k = \varphi_k', \quad (1)$$

where ε_k , γ_k , and χ_k are the axial and shear deformations and the bending curvature and the superscript ' indicates a spatial derivative with respect to the longitudinal coordinate. The constitutive relationships are:

$$N_k = A_k \varepsilon_k, \quad M_k = D_k \chi_k, \quad V_k = G_k \gamma_k, \quad (2)$$

where D_k , A_k and G_k are the bending, extensional and shear stiffnesses of the sub-laminate defined using lamination theory from the elastic constants and geometry of the laminae comprising the sub-laminate. The layup of each sub-beam is assumed to satisfy conditions of homogeneity and orthotropy.

Normal and tangential tractions T^N and T^S act along the lower (subscript $k, k+1$) and upper (subscript $k-1, k$) surfaces of the k -th sub-beam. They may represent externally applied tractions on the beam surfaces, contact and cohesive tractions or the action of the core. Equilibrium of sub-beam k is given by:

$$M_k' - V_k - 1/2 h_k (T_{k, k+1}^S + T_{k-1, k}^S) = \rho_m I_k \ddot{\varphi}_k, \quad (3)$$

$$V'_k - T_{k,k+1}^N + T_{k-1,k}^N = \rho_m S_k \ddot{w}_k, \quad (4)$$

$$N'_k - T_{k,k+1}^S + T_{k-1,k}^S = \rho_m S_k \ddot{u}_k, \quad (5)$$

where the terms on the right hand sides account for the inertia of the sub-beam and the dot indicates a derivative with respect to time. In the static model the right hand sides are equal to zero.

The interaction between the generic stacked sub-beams k and $k+1$ is described by an interface law that relates the interfacial tractions, $T_{k,k+1}^N$ and $T_{k,k+1}^S$, to the interfacial displacements

$$w_{k,k+1}^N = w_{k+1} - w_k, \quad w_{k,k+1}^S = [u_{k+1} + \varphi_{k+1} h_{k+1}/2] - [u_k - \varphi_k h_k/2] \quad (6).$$

and depend on the specific behavior that the interface is called to describe in the model. The interface laws are approximated by piecewise linear curves.

Both static and dynamic models assume elastic normal contact between sub-beams along the delaminations and neglect friction. The interfacial tractions are given by $T_{k,k+1}^N = -k_{k,k+1}^{Ncont} w_{k,k+1}^N$ and $T_{k,k+1}^S = 0$, where

$$k_{k,k+1}^{cont} = H(-w_{k,k+1}^N) \frac{2E_T}{h_k + h_{k+1}}, \quad (7)$$

E_T is the through-thickness modulus of the material and $H(\cdot)$ is the Heaviside step function ($H(\zeta) = \{ 1 \text{ if } \zeta > 0, 0 \text{ otherwise} \}$). When the interface is used to represent perfect adhesion between sub-beams in the intact portion of the beam in the dynamic model, a steep linear elastic branch is used up to a critical value of the interfacial displacement. The normal and tangential stiffnesses are chosen to be very high to minimize errors due to the introduction of fictitious compliant surfaces in the body. The interaction between the lowest sub-beams and the Winkler foundation is described by an interface where $w_{k+1}, u_{k+1}, \varphi_{k+1} = 0$ (Eq.(6)). If elastic-plastic core-crushing is assumed, the unloading of the cohesive law is assumed to be linearly elastic with a constant stiffness equal to the initial response of the foundation and a residual displacement.

Delamination propagation

The delaminations are assumed to propagate collinearly. In the static model the J-integral is applied to evaluate the energy release rate of each delamination. The expression for a crack tip separating beam segments j (ahead of the tip), k and $k+1$ (in the wake of the crack, Fig 1a) is [9]:

$$\mathcal{G} = J = \frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_{i=k}^{k+1} \left(\frac{M_i^2}{EI_i} + \frac{6}{5} \frac{V_i^2}{Gh_i} + \frac{N_i^2}{Eh_i} - 2V_i \varphi_i \right) - \frac{M_j^2}{EI_j} - \frac{6}{5} \frac{V_j^2}{Gh_j} - \frac{N_j^2}{Eh_j} + 2V_j \varphi_j \right) \quad (8)$$

In the dynamic model interfaces extend in the non-delaminated part of the beam and define all potential fracture planes between sub-beams (Fig. 1b). Fracture propagation is directly controlled by the behaviour of the cohesive interfaces in the intact part of the beam. Critical mode I, w_0^N , and mode II, w_0^S , interfacial displacements define the end of the initial elastic steep branch used in the intact part of the beam. In this paper the interfacial tractions are assumed to vanish beyond the critical interfacial displacements and the areas under the cohesive traction-displacement laws represent the mode I and mode II fracture energies of the interface $G_{Icr} = 1/2 k_{k,k+1}^N (w_0^N)^2$ and $G_{IIcr} = 1/2 k_{k,k+1}^S (w_0^S)^2$; with this assumption the size of the cohesive zone at a delamination tip is small, the crack is in small scale yielding conditions and the interface model can be used to simulate perfectly brittle fracture and reproduce LEFM results [10-13]. Failure envelopes for mixed-mode fracture are then defined in terms of relative crack displacements or energy release rate components:

$$\left(H(w_{k,k+1}^N) \frac{w_{k,k+1}^N}{w_0^N} \right)^r + \left| \frac{w_{k,k+1}^S}{w_0^S} \right|^r = 1 \quad \text{or} \quad \left(\frac{G_I}{G_{Icr}} \right)^{r-1} + \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIcr}} \right)^{r-1} = 1 \quad (9)$$

Solution of the static model

In the static model, any configurations corresponding to a given state of contact or cohesion between the sub-beams is described by subdividing the beam into sub-sets of stacked sub-beams, each one characterized by the same state of the interface along the longitudinal axis. Each sub-set is then solved as a set of stacked beams joined by linear elastic springs, laying on a linear elastic foundation. A closed form solution is obtained that describes static and kinematic fields of each sub-set as a function of its boundary conditions. The imposition of continuity conditions between horizontally adjacent sub-sets and of the overall boundary conditions of the delaminated beam leads to the rigorous reduction of the initial differential equilibrium problem to a discrete problem to be solved numerically. An initial contact/cohesion state of the overall beam is assumed to start an iterative procedure where the contact/cohesion state is checked and updated at each iteration until convergence is obtained. If the loading conditions or the progression of damage induce unloading of the nonlinear foundation in its plastic phase, the problem requires an incremental approach.

Solution of the dynamic model

In the dynamic model, the solution is found by discretizing the problem using unidimensional space and time grids and applying a finite difference numerical scheme with second order accuracy. The governing equations for all beam sections corresponding to each grid point are combined into a single matrix equation and boundary conditions are applied with all derivatives approximated as one-sided differences. The final matrix equation at time step n is of the form

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{v}}^{(n)} = \mathbf{K}^{(n)} \mathbf{v}^{(n)} + \mathbf{F}^{(n)} \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{v}^{(n)}$ is a vector of the displacements w, u, φ for all beam segments in each beam section, \mathbf{M} is the mass matrix and $\mathbf{F}^{(n)}$ contains all contributions from uniformly applied

loads. The stiffness matrix \mathbf{K}^n depends on time due to the non-linearity of the interfaces. The time integration technique is based on the implicit, unconditionally stable, alpha-method of Chung and Hulbert [14], which maximizes numerical dissipation of high-frequency oscillations. The regions of contact and cohesion, which are unknown *a priori*, are defined through an iterative numerical procedure.

RESULTS

A beam equilibrates applied loads by transferring them to its constraints. If the constraints are located at the beam ends, the load affects the internal forces for the whole length of the beam; if instead the constraints are continuously distributed along the beam, as in the case of a Winkler foundation, the effect of the load decreases at increasing distances from the load position. When the beam is delaminated, the interaction between the beam and the foundation induces shielding of the fracture parameters at the crack tips (namely a decrease of the fracture parameters with respect to the values for the cracks in the absence of the foundation).

Fig. 2 Dimensionless energy release rate as a function of delamination lengths in a cantilever beam on an elastic foundation with one (dashed line) and two (solid line) delaminations.

Dashed lines in the diagrams of Figures 2 and 3 show the dimensionless energy release rate of a single delamination crack in a homogeneous and isotropic cantilever beam subject to a concentrated force P at the free end, with Young modulus E and thickness h , lying on an elastic foundation with modulus k , as a function of the normalized length of the delamination and for different beam-foundation stiffness ratios, kh/E . The delamination is located at one third of the beam thickness above the foundation. The energy release rate for a given delamination length decreases on increasing the beam-foundation stiffness ratio. As the stiffness ratio grows above 10^{-4} , the dependence loses its monotonicity and a maximum appears for intermediate lengths of the delamination. Further increase of the stiffness ratio moves the position of the maximum towards the loaded end of the beam and a minimum appears (see Figure 3) close to the other end. The shielding effect then becomes strong enough to induce a stable growth of the delamination for a large range of lengths along the beam.

Fig. 3 Dimensionless energy release rate as a function of delamination lengths in a cantilever beam on an elastic foundation with one (dashed line) and two (solid line) delaminations.

Figure 4a shows a similar local barrier to the propagation of the crack in terms of normalized critical load for crack propagation in a beam with no end constraint and a higher length to thickness ratio ($a/h = 150$). The diagram shows the dimensionless load as a function of the normalized length of the delamination. In this case, the barrier is followed by a sharp decrease and by an increasing branch with an almost linear trend (the local softening at the end of the beam is a boundary effect). The presence of a local minimum of the energy release rate and the corresponding local maximum of the critical load are related to the oscillatory nature of the solution of a beam on an elastic foundation where shear force and bending moment oscillate around zero along the longitudinal coordinate of the beam with periodically distributed local maxima. Due to these oscillations, the analytical solution of a simplified model where delamination opening and elastic interpenetration are neglected (constrained model) predicts periodically distributed local maxima of the critical load as a function of the delamination length. This solution well approximates the solution of the full model (that accounts for elastic contact and opening) shown in Figure 4a up to the first maximum, in the range where the crack is essentially mode II in both models. However, after the first maximum, the solution obtained with the full model becomes almost linear and deeply differs from the simplified solution with its periodic maxima. When the delamination is long enough, the bottom portion of the beam is constrained by the foundation to oscillate along the axis direction around its rest position, while the upper portion, which is not constrained by the foundation, deforms and induce important opening of the delamination along its entire length. This modification of the behaviour deeply affects the stress field at the crack tip, which becomes mainly mode I.

The effects of the through-thickness position of the delamination on the critical load for crack propagation are shown in Figure 4b, where the dimensionless critical load is described as a function of the delamination length for three different delaminations located at the midplane and at the upper and lower thirds of the thickness. A clear trend shown by the diagram is that the lower is the delamination, the easier is to propagate it. Equally spaced delaminations in a cantilever beam without an elastic foundation

propagate simultaneously under both static and dynamic loading conditions [7,8]; the results shown in Figure 4b suggest that the presence of the foundation could give rise to a different behaviour, where delaminations closer to the foundation are more critical. And indeed, an exemplary static analysis performed to investigate crack propagation in the case of two equally spaced delaminations on an elastic foundation shows that crack propagation is stable and simultaneous until the delaminations reach the energy barrier; for longer delaminations, important opening takes place along the surfaces of the lower delamination that continues to propagate while the upper delamination arrest.

Fig. 4 Dimensionless critical load for crack propagation in a beam with high length to thickness ratio on an elastic foundation. (a) Central delamination; (b) different positions. (Fracture criterion: $G = G_I + G_{II} = G_{cr}$ with G_{cr} the fracture energy)

The interaction of multiple delaminations has important effects on energy release rates in laminated beams [7,8]. An example of these effects in sandwich beams is shown in Figure 2 and 3 (solid lines), where the dimensionless energy release rate of the lower delamination in the delaminated beam described in the inset is shown as a function of its normalized length. The presence of an upper delamination of fixed length deeply modifies the energy release rates of the lower delamination with respect to the single delamination solution (shown by the dashed lines). Moreover, as the foundation-beam stiffness ratio increases, the sudden transition that occurs when the delamination tips come close to each others in a laminated beam with no foundation decreases and then becomes negligible.

The behaviour in the case of dynamic loading shows similarities with the static problem; however, inertial effects enrich the response of the beam that presents new features. Figure 5 depicts the time history of crack propagation in a doubly delaminated cantilever beam lying on an elastic foundation and subjected to a triangular pulse force applied at the free end. The upper (and shorter) delamination starts to propagate first and approaches the lower crack tip; afterwards, they propagate simultaneously under conditions that are approximately mode II and then arrest at approximately two thirds of the length of the beam. After a short break, they continue to propagate up to the end of the beam. The second phase of propagation takes place after the load has been removed,

in the free vibration phase, and is a consequence of dynamic effects. In this phase the lower delamination opens and the lowest arm of the delaminated beam, which is attached to the foundation, oscillates on its own at a frequency higher than that of the upper arms that move upward. This phenomenon induces an important mode I component of the energy release rate at the crack tips that triggers the second phase of propagation of both cracks at a speed comparable to that of the forced vibration phase.

Fig. 5 Time history of the the delamination lengths in a multiply delaminated beam on an elastic foundation subject to a triangular pulse load (c_L = longitudinal wave speed)

CONCLUSIONS

The work deals with the interaction of different damage mechanisms in face sheets and core of composite sandwich beams subject to static and dynamic out-of-plane loadings. The reference problem of a delaminated beam, which represents an upper face sheet, on a nonlinear Winkler foundation, which represents the core, has been analysed. The results define and explain some general features of the effects of the skin-core interaction on damage propagation.

The results from static analyses obtained under the assumption of an elastic foundation show a generalized phenomenon of shielding of the fracture parameters that is controlled by the foundation-beam stiffness ratio and by the through-thickness position of the delamination (delaminations close to the foundation are less shielded). For high enough stiffness ratios, a local minimum of the energy release rate as a function of the delamination crack length appears at a distance from the applied load that depends mainly on the foundation-beam stiffness ratio. This minimum represents a localized energy barrier to crack propagation. In sufficiently long beams, this barrier is described by a local sharp maximum in the curve that relates the critical load for crack propagation to crack length. After the maximum, the curve then shows an almost linear dependence on the delamination length; this behaviour is a consequence of the delamination openings that arise when the delamination tip is beyond the barrier and induce an important mode I component at the crack tip. If the openings were eliminated, for instance by the action of a through-thickness reinforcement, the model would predict a periodic series of energy barriers controlled by the oscillations of the beam on the elastic foundation. The foundation-beam stiffness ratio also controls phenomena of local

amplification which occur when the delamination tips come close to each other. The results from dynamic analyses show that inertia effects modify the crack loading conditions and may reduce the effects of the energy barrier observed in the quasi-static cases. The interaction with the core generates oscillations in the arms of the delaminated beam that are characterized by different frequencies and amplitudes and induce openings of the delaminations. These openings lead to important mode I loading conditions at crack tip that typically favour crack propagation.

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